

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Characterization of a commercial High-Performance RISC-V System-on-Chip for space applications</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA10-347</i>
General application	<i>Space and high-reliability applications</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE and TID</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Luigi Dilillo (IES/UM/CNRS)</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>André M. P. Mattos (IES/UM), Douglas A. Santos (IES/UM)</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>07/09/2024 to 09/09/2024</i>
Facility	<i>PIF, Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>8h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

Modern space applications are increasingly demanding reliable processors with higher computational capabilities for missions with tight budgets and fast deployment. Despite this need, the options that meet these criteria are scarce or non-existent. Therefore, the space sector gradually increased the usage of Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) and had to develop dedicated mitigation strategies to maintain the required radiation reliability margins. Recent research and market trends have shown interest in adopting the RISC-V processors for high-reliability applications since the openness of this architecture enables customizations to increase their radiation reliability. In this context, we propose investigating a powerful RISC-V-based system introduced recently for reliability-oriented sectors: Microchip's PolarFire System-on-Chip (SoC). Therefore, our proposal's main targets are performing an in-depth analysis of this RISC-V multiprocessor reliability and assessing methodologies for radiation testing of complex commercial SoCs. For this purpose, we propose an experiment using high-energy protons to analyze and characterize Single-Event Effects (SEEs).

Experiment test report

The System Under Test (SUT), PolarFire SoC, integrates a powerful 64-bit 5x core RISC-V processor with the PolarFire SONOS-based FPGA. The multi-core cluster is split into a compact monitoring core and 4x applications cores with more performance and resources. It includes L1 and L2 caches with Single-Error Correction and Double-Error Detection (SECCED). Many peripherals and high-speed interfaces for the FPGA are connected to the main bus. To accomplish the test objectives, we exploited these built-in hardware observability features (e.g., SECCED reporting, watchdog timers) and custom software fixtures (e.g., exceptions, step-by-step output checking) to instrument processing workloads. Fig.1 shows the SUT block diagram.

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Fig.1 - PolarFire SoC block diagram.

In this study, we focused on the multiprocessor cluster, from which the monitor core was used to test an application core during irradiation. For that, the application core (HART1) executes a performance benchmark composed of a set of 15 workloads (Embench v1.0) adapted for the context of radiation testing by reporting its context to the monitoring core and the benchmark results. The monitoring core (HART0) was responsible for handling exceptions from the cluster and forwarding the benchmark results to the host side. We provided two adapted implementations of Embench, one as a baremetal application executing all workloads in sequence and the other as an RTOS-based (FreeRTOS) program that preempts workloads to provide a similar access time to the processor resources.

For the test setup, we use a compact test board (system-on-module) in combination with a custom interface board, avoiding unnecessary hardware features that are prone to affecting the experiment. The custom interface board provides robust power/communication interfaces, current/temperature reporting, and timestamp synchronization for proper testing. Fig.2 presents the proposed test setup, and Fig.3 presents the test setup ready for irradiation in the PIF beamline at PSI.

Fig.2 - Test setup for the proposed experiment

Fig.3 - Experimental setup mounted at PIF beamline (PSI).

We selected the following proton energies for testing: 30, 50, 100, 150, and 200 MeV. The primary proton energy (200 MeV) was degraded using copper plates introduced in the beam path to generate the required energies. We used proton fluxes of approximately 3×10^7 to 5×10^7 p/cm²/s for the main test runs. The beam provided 10% homogeneity for the selected irradiation area (20 mm x 20 mm) and beam energies. For this experiment, the accumulated fluence reached 9.09×10^{11} p/cm², considering both SUTs (*mpfs1* and *mpfs2*) and benchmarks.

The experiment focused on SEEs, but due to the fluxes and energies used for the proton irradiation, the SUTs reached high levels of TID, approximately 67.4 krad(Si) in the worst case. For this reason, we evaluated the impact and biases caused by TID, which showed no major impact on the SEE results nor functional losses, such as FPGA reprogramming, which is known to be sensitive in the case of FPGAs with non-volatile configuration memories. In this document, we report the experimental results for the baremetal benchmark, focusing on SEUs and SEFIs. Further analysis and results are subject to future publications.

During the experiment, several SEUs were reported, representing 2631 single-events. From all monitored structures, only data/instruction L1 caches from E51 and U54 (203 and 598 events, respectively) and the unified L2 cache (1830 events) were observed and reported as:

1. **hart0_l1i_corr**: correctable events on HART0 instruction L1 cache
2. **hart1_l1i_corr**: correctable events on HART1 instruction L1 cache
3. **hart1_l1d_corr**: correctable events on HART1 data L1 cache
4. **l2_corr**: correctable on L2 cache (any HART)
5. **l2_uncorr**: uncorrectable on L2 cache (any HART).

Fig.4 presents the SEU cross sections for each group mentioned, combining *mpfs1* and *mpfs2* results. The error bars represent a 95% confidence interval with a 10% beam fluence uncertainty. Correctable errors in the L2 cache present the highest contribution to the cross section. Uncorrectable errors are rare events when compared to the other reported groups. Thus, their lower number of events significantly impacts the error bars.

Fig.4 - SEU cross sections during baremetal benchmark.

Regarding SEFIs, a total of 35 events were recorded, which were classified based on their error signatures:

1. **traps**: when a trap was triggered in any HART
2. **hangs**: when the MSS stopped responding (after a defined period of 2 minutes)
3. **mismatch**: benchmark output error in a workload (when the result is different from expected)
4. **hart0_wdt**: watchdog timer on HART0
5. **hart1_wdt**: watchdog timer on HART1
6. **hart1_bus**: when HART1 failed to load/store from the coherent switch (TileLink)
7. **curr_spike**: when a significantly above average current transient occurred just before a hang.

Fig.5 presents the SEFI cross sections. The error bars represent a 95% confidence interval with a 10% beam fluence uncertainty.

Fig.5 - SEFI cross sections during baremetal benchmark.

In this experiment, we investigated the reliability of baremetal applications on RISC-V multiprocessors of the Microchip PolarFire SoC (MPFS). For that, we presented the SEE characterization using high-energy protons with tailored benchmarks for reliability evaluation. The SUTs presented various correctable errors, but only a few faults propagated to cause benchmark failures or other critical behaviors. In this report, we presented preliminary irradiation results that will be extended in future work, covering the FreeRTOS benchmark and providing a detailed investigation of propagation, masking, and impact of the observed faults.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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